
ACOUSTIC VISUALIZATION OF SHOCK CELLS IN AN ORIFICE JET USING NEARFIELD ACOUSTIC HOLOGRAPHY (NAH) TECHNIQUE

Nitesh Anerao, Vikas Bhargav and K. Srinivasan

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India

e-mail: nitane.iitm@gmail.com, vikasbhargav92@gmail.com, ksri@iitm.ac.in

Many engineering applications as aircraft jets, rockets etc. cause noise related issues that potentially lead to a reduced overall efficiency and sometimes hazardous working environments. Many standards and norms are set in place to avoid any environmental or health issue. Hence a large amount of research has been done and in progress to reduce irksome noise and to cater the norms. However to reduce noise effectively, noise source localization and characterization of highly emissive regions is of real importance. Once the source regions are identified, many active and passive techniques can be effectively devised to mitigate or control noise. Many effective source localization techniques have been used in the past for this purpose. This study deals with the application of phased array technique called Near-field Acoustic Holography (NAH) for the localization of acoustic sources. The algorithm is initially tested for simulated monopole source and experimentally validated on stationary speaker source to finally apply it localizing jet sources. In this work, NAH is potentially used as an acoustic tool to visualize shock cells arising in orifice jet plume at screech frequencies. Acoustic source mapping is specifically done for screech tones since it the most dominant and major contributor among all other noise sources in jet. It can be used to understand noise characteristics in aircraft or rocket jet plumes originating from orifice or nozzles. Experiments are carried in semi-anechoic facility at different Nozzle Pressure Ratios (NPR) for orifice jet. In order to effectively cover the jet domain, an improvisation is made to planar array setup and a linear array is used. The linear array is scanned in transverse direction (y-direction) and finally all scans are patched together to get a proper acoustic map. The disturbance in phase due to patching of linear array and non-stationarity associated with jet leads to source information loss that is taken care by placing set of microphones near the source. These microphones are used as a reference to get more detailed information about the source characteristics. If the source location is unknown as in case of jets, reference microphones are kept throughout the region of interest. The acoustic field generated by dominant sources is captured by reference microphones which is cross correlated and processed with array microphones to generate a partial field of interest. With the help of reference microphones the whole acoustic field is systematically segregated in terms of partial fields, ranked on basis of source acoustic strength. The acoustic based holography measurement is done in tandem with density based shadowgraph technique to capture shock cells in tandem. The acoustic visualization of shock cells at screech frequencies done using NAH gives a clear image of highly emissive regions in jet plume and is also verified with shadowgraph image thus giving a different dimension altogether in understanding of jet characteristics.

1. Introduction

One of the most widely known problems in acoustic domain is identification of source so as to mitigate its after effects. Extensive research is in progress in automobile and aviation industry pertaining to identification and quantification of sources for its full-fledged control. There exists variety of techniques that are used to serve the purpose. In this work, Near-field Acoustic Holography (NAH) [1] is used for source localization.

In jets, there exist a large number of multi-frequency non-stationary sources which are partially correlated. Also, jet domain is particularly large to cover using array of microphones. A large number of microphones are required to serve the purpose which is not economically feasible. Hence to localize jet noise sources, an efficient algorithm is required considering the above factors. Significant work has been carried out in the past to create a map of the acoustic sources in jets under various operating conditions using different localization techniques customized to obtain better resolution. Beam forming techniques, deconvolution algorithms like DAMAS, CLEAN, TIDY and its variants are a few of the phased array approaches that have been employed in the past. However, most of these techniques used were based on far field approach which did not account for evanescent wave components present in the near field of source. Hence resolution was compromised which is very essential for mapping multiple partially correlated sources in jets. In order to overcome above problems faced, an algorithm known as multi reference Partial Field Decomposition (PFD) [2], [3] based Near-field Acoustic Holography (NAH) which is a modified addition over basic NAH algorithm is used. It employs scanning technique to cover the necessary jet domain in number of patches and then maps the dominant sources accordingly. It uses the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) and cross spectral measurements with multiple reference microphones to resolve different dominant sources in the jet domain. Each reference microphone placed near the source helps in capturing important information about it. Thus, the measured sound field is decomposed into a number of coherent partial fields that are mutually incoherent. The basic objective of this work is to use the advent of NAH technique to visualize shock cells arising in orifice jet plume at screech frequencies. Acoustic source mapping is specifically done for screech tones since it the most dominant and major contributor among all other noise sources in jet. This work can be used as a basis to understand noise characteristics in aircraft or rocket jet plumes originating from orifice or nozzles.

2. Formulation

2.1 Nearfield Acoustic Holography (NAH)

Assuming that the sound field (function of space and time) created by some sources in a 3-D region of interest satisfies the homogeneous wave equation, the Fourier transformation of which gives homogeneous Helmholtz equation as,

$$\nabla^2 \tilde{p}(r, \omega) + k^2 \tilde{p}(r, \omega) = 0. \quad (1)$$

The fundamental of NAH lies in utilizing the known Green's function G with certain boundary conditions to solve Helmholtz Eq. (1). Here, since homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition on surface S , we get solution as Rayleigh's first Integral,

$$\tilde{p}(r, \omega) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \iint \left\{ \tilde{p}(r_s, \omega) \frac{\partial G}{\partial n}(r|r_s) \right\} d^2 r_s \quad (2)$$

On observation, Eq. (2) seems to be 2-D convolution that relates source plane with any measurement plane. With correct discretization and with consideration of planar co-ordinates (x, y, z) , we finally get,

$$\tilde{p}(x, y, z) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\hat{p}(k_x, k_y, z_h) \hat{G}'(k_x, k_y, z - z_h) \right) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\hat{p}(k_x, k_y, z_h) e^{ik_z(z-z_h)} \right) \quad (3)$$

where, $\hat{G}'(k_x, k_y, z) = e^{iz(k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2)^{1/2}} = e^{izk_z}$ is inverse Green's propagator, (x, y, z_h) represents measurement plane and k_x, k_y and k_z are wavenumbers in respective directions and $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$.

To identify source information, which is the main purpose of this work, consider any plane (x, y, z) as source plane denoted by (x, y, z_s) . we finally derive to:

$$\tilde{p}(x, y, z_s) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\hat{p}(k_x, k_y, z_h) e^{ik_z(z_s - z_h)} \right) \quad (4)$$

$G_p^{-1} = e^{ik_z(z_s - z_h)}$ where, is a inverse Green's propagator.

The particle velocity can also be derived using the Euler's equation that relates the gradient of pressure and particle velocity,

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \vec{p}(t) \quad (5)$$

Taking temporal and two-dimensional spatial Fourier transform of equation (5), the particle velocity in normal direction to measurement plane is written as,

$$\tilde{w}(x, y, z_s) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\frac{k_z}{\rho_0 c k} \hat{p}(k_x, k_y, z_h) e^{ik_z(z_s - z_h)} \right) \quad (6)$$

where, $G_v^{-1} = \frac{k_z}{\rho_0 c k} e^{ik_z(z_s - z_h)}$ is inverse Green's velocity propagator.

Using Equations 4 and 5, intensity can be mapped as:

$$\tilde{I}(x, y, z_s) = \tilde{w}(x, y, z_s) * \tilde{p}(x, y, z_s)$$

Since the usage of NAH technique involves dealing with matrix inversion which may result in ill-conditioning owing to singular values associated with noise. The data is treated using Tikhonov regularization with a correct parameter estimator to get proper localization of sound sources.

2.2 Scan and patch based Partial field Decomposition (PFD)

The scan and patch based NAH is used in applications where it is not able to cover the entire domain at a time using array of microphones. This method of patch and scan has been particularly used in jet noise source localization [4] where domain for mapping is very large. Partial field decomposition (PFD) is one such technique that uses set of reference microphones outside the array near a source to decompose the measured sound field into set of linearly independent partial fields. The decomposed partial field \hat{P} is calculated using singular values obtained from reference microphones cross-spectral matrix and from transfer matrix relating array and reference microphone measurements. The non-stationarity of sources, associated noise and the data variations owing to scans is also taken care [4] to get,

$$\hat{P} = H_{rp(scan)}^T U^*_{(avg.)} \sum_{(scan)}^{1/2} = C_{rp(scan)}^T U^*_{(avg.)} \sum_{(scan)}^{-1/2}$$

where the i^{th} column vector of \hat{P} represents the i^{th} partial field and * represents complex conjugate. H_{rp} is the transfer matrix that connects the reference signals and the measured field signals on the hologram surface where $H_{rp} = C_{rp} C_{rr}$. The crossspectral matrices C_{rr} and C_{rp} are providing correlation between reference microphone signals and array microphone signals respectively. U and \sum are obtained from Singular value decomposition of C_{rr} . Subscripts $(scan)$ and $(avg.)$ are estimates computed over each scan and estimates averaged over all scans respectively.

3. Test setup and Measurements

The experiment is carried out in semi-anechoic chamber having a cut-off frequency of 700 Hz. A cold jet facility is housed inside the anechoic chamber where two vents are provided on the opposite walls, front vent for jet discharge and behind one for jet entrainment. Aero-acoustic test facility is explained in detail [5].

3.1 NAH setup

In this experiment, a linear array comprising of 20 microphones spaced 10 mm apart is used. Mi-

crophones (Kingstate model KECG3642TFA) used in this setup are quarter inch, omni-directional electret condenser microphones which have almost flat spectral response in the audible range (100 Hz to 20 kHz) with an uncertainty of ± 3 dB. The array is at a distance of 60 mm from jet centerline, which is six times sensor separation distance. Seven scans, all parallel to jet axis and equidistant to each other at one sensor separation distance i.e. 10 mm, is taken in same plane. Finally, all seven scans are stitched together to map a scan of 200x60 mm. When a jet emerging from 10 mm orifice attains steady flow, data is acquired at a sampling rate of 34 kHz using Agilent U2331A USB modular multifunction DAQ. In this experimental setup, all nine reference microphones are used at desired positions as shown in Fig. 1. It is made sure that microphones used in this setup are at a distance where readings are not affected by the flow regime. The schematic of the linear and reference microphone setup is shown in Fig. 1. The orifice used is made up of Mild steel and is manufactured using Electro Discharge Machining (EDM) process.

Figure 1. Schematic of linear array and reference microphone setup for orifice jet NAH experiments

3.2 Shadowgraph Setup

In order to reveal the flow characteristics of jet, shadowgraph imaging is done. This will serve as a validation for acoustic based imaging. The basic principle involves changes in refractive index of flow media due to inhomogeneous density gradients to record an image. From analysis of shadow effect, it follows that the visible signal depends on the second derivative of the refractive index of fluid [6]. Since second derivative is involved, sharp variation in density gradient is required for proper imaging. Particularly in compressible jet flows involving shock waves, alterations of the gas density occurs with extremely intense change in curvature of the density profile which is captured as a shadowgraph image. The study done in this section is to visualize the shock cells emerging from imperfectly expanded orifice jet. The dimensioned optical setup shown in Fig. 2 that serves the

Figure 2. Schematic setup of shadowgraph – flow visualization technique

above purpose involves the usage of a light source, condenser lens, pinpoint slit, beam splitter, two bi-convex lenses and a camera in depicted positions. The shadowgraph image obtained is then typically compared with the acoustic holography image obtained using NAH setup.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Blowdown Study

In order to get comprehensive information about the various sound sources in orifice jet and particularly to understand the zones of screech tones in a frequency vs Nozzle Pressure ratio (NPR) plot, the blowdown study is carried out. In this study, a jet setup is used to first compress the air upto maximum gauge pressure possible which is 6 bars in this case. Once the highest pressure is reached, compressor is stopped and the jet is initiated. A microphone is set at such a distance where it is not affected by jet directly. In this study, microphone is positioned 30ϕ from jet centreline at emission angle of 90° . The acoustic data is recorded in accordance with continuous pressure readings inside settling chamber sensed by piezo-resistive pressure transducer (Endevco model 8510C-100). The data acquisition is done at regular time interval of 5 seconds for sampling rate of 40 kHz till atmospheric pressure is reached. The data acquired is then processed in Matlab 2015a to enumerate noise sources as shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Blowdown study mapping various noise sources for orifice jet

Figure 3 shows the result of blowdown study in terms of SPL plot highlighting regions of sources in orifice jet ($\phi=10\text{mm}$). This study helps us to understand the characteristics of various noise regions throughout the frequency range. It also gives an input to map at specific region of interest to trace shock cells using NAH technique. The noise generation is due to high velocity flows causing turbulent eddies generated by shearing flow. These eddies contribute to different frequency noise depending on its size which can be calculated using Strouhal number (St). Noises in any jet are either tonal or broadband in nature. Broadband noise containing turbulent mixing noise and shock associated noise broadly covers whole domain of frequencies in jet whereas tonal noise including screech tones and transonic tones are specific and zonal in nature with respect to NPR and frequency as seen in Fig. 3. It can be observed that the screech tones in particular are the most dominant of all noises and contribute maximum in terms of sound level (dB). Screech tone is a consequence of feedback loop generated between shock cells and nozzle lip where shock cells acts as a diaphragm oscillating at certain frequencies with respect to NPR. Hence, acoustic study in terms of source mapping for these shock cells at screech frequencies with respect to particular NPR is carried out.

4.2 Shock cell visualization using Shadowgraph and NAH theory

The acoustic intensity map visualizing shock cells at screech frequencies of 10500, 11240, 11950 and 12910 Hz along with luminescence density based shadowgraph image at respective NPR's is illustrated in Fig. 4. The relevant or averaged partial field is only highlighted and shown because all other

partial field seem to have very less information about source. It is well noted and understood that for proper point to point mapping of shock cell position in acoustic image with respect to shadowgraph image, the pixel size, image focus, reconstruction distance and resolution has to be perfectly matched. Since that is another area of research, it is decided to focus more on theory validation rather than correct scaling of acoustically visualized shock cells with shadowgraph image.

Figure 5. Shadowgraph and NAH image in tandem for different conditions : (a) 5.50 NPR and 10500 Hz, (b) 5.0 NPR and 11240 Hz , (c) 4.50 NPR and 11950 Hz, (d) 4.0 NPR and 12910 Hz.

In addition, quantification of source is a problem since data is reconstructed at higher stand-off distance. This amplification problem may also be due to reference microphones that are placed in near vicinity of source, but on one hand we get improved resolution in localization. Hence, in this work our focus is mainly on localization of source and not on quantification. Acoustic intensity mapping is preferred in this work instead of acoustic pressure or velocity since it seemed to characterize sound sources with better resolution. The acoustic camera used for this setup helps in visualizing the shock cells at screech frequencies thus giving fair idea about dominant region in flow of 10 mm diameter orifice jet at respective NPR to further use active or passive control for noise eradication.

4.3 Validation of NAH theory on orifice jets

In order to validate the theory for proper justification, acoustic mapping of tonal and non-tonal region is done. Figure 5 shows acoustic map for two conditions (1) and (2) where mapping at screech frequency is kept as reference and either NPR or operating frequency region is altered. In plot (a) of condition 1, mapping is done at 5.5 NPR and frequency of 10500 Hz which is a region of screech tone as referred from Fig. 3. The plots (b) with 5.5 NPR and 5000 Hz frequency and (c) with 3.0 NPR and 10500 Hz frequency of condition (1) points out the turbulent mixing noise regions which is a broadband noise as seen from Fig. 3. In plot (a) of condition 2, mapping is done at

5.0 NPR and frequency of 11240 Hz which is a region of screech tone as referred from Fig. 3. The plots (b) with 5.0 NPR and 6000 Hz frequency and (c) with 3.5 NPR and 11240 Hz frequency of condition (2) points out the turbulent mixing noise regions indicating broadband noise as seen from Fig. 3.

Figure 5. Acoustic intensity mapping for condition 1 and 2.

The alteration done with changing either NPR or frequency with respect to the screech tone region in both conditions is seen to fall in turbulent mixing region zone as seen from Fig. 3 whose amplitude with respect to screech tone is very less. To quantify the amplitude magnitude all the plots (a), (b) and (c) of conditions 1 and 2 are kept at same strength levels to have a proper comparison. It is seen that non-tonal regions did not seem to even have a trace of source, which justifies that the tonal map shown is actually shock cell at that particular frequency and NPR only.

5. Conclusions

It can be concluded that the NAH methodology and the experimental setup used effectively localized shock cells at screech frequencies in jet plume emerging from 10 mm diameter orifice. Shock cells at dominant screech frequencies are recorded in tandem using light based shadowgraph technique and acoustics based NAH technique. The shadowgraph based visualization of shock cells helps understand the flow characteristics whereas NAH mapping helps comprehend acoustic features of shock cells at screech frequencies. With flow and acoustic characterization done for screech tone, which is the highest noise contributor, passive or active treatment can be devised to reduce overall noise levels.

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